

THE ROLE OF ORAL CAVITY MICROORGANISMS IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF INFLAMMATION AND SOMATIC PATHOLOGY

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Introduction: The review presents the modern concept of the oral microbiome, its species diversity, the properties of microbial associations and their effect on the immunobiological resistance of the organism, development of chronic inflammation and two leading infectious and inflammatory diseases (dental caries and periodontal diseases). There is briefly summarized information about the presence and nature of the relationship between the composition of periodontal microorganisms and concomitant somatic diseases: in atherosclerotic plaques in cardiovascular diseases, with pathology of the gastrointestinal tract, respiratory system and other organs and systems.

Key words: microbiology of the oral cavity, inflammation, dental caries, periodontal diseases, interrelation of oral microbiome and somatic diseases.

Annotation: The association between infection of the maxillofacial system and diseases of other anatomical parts of the body was known more than 100 years ago, so it was necessary to continue to explore common etiological and pathophysiological factors of these diseases. However, it was only with the advent of molecular genetic methods that the biological study of microorganisms (microbiomes), one of the main inducers of the development and progression of inflammatory diseases of the dental and jaw systems, began in earnest. Microorganisms live in mucous membranes, the back of the tongue, gingivitis, oral fluid, plaque, etc., and obtain the necessary proteins, carbohydrates, amino acids, inorganic substances, etc. from the oral fluid. The microbiome of this

ecological niche, which occupies only 0.03-0.05m² in the oral cavity, contains representatives of 530-700 stable species [23, 27]. In addition to the representative bacteria actinomycetes, Campylobacter, capnocytophaga, corinebacterium, fusobacterium, nickeria, granulicatella, prevotella, streptococcus, and veillonella, the anaerobic primordial bacteria filifactor, fusobacterium, parvimonas, Bacillus subtilis, Porphyromonas, Prevotera, Tannerella, Treponema, Candida albicans, C. tropicalis, C. pseudotropicalis, C. Protozoa Entamoeba gingivalis and Trichomonas tenax, Mycoplasma M. et al. [2, 3, 6, 10]. Microorganisms that accumulate in plaque (plaque and tartar) are, in modern interpretation, only biofilms composed of multi-bacterial communities. [4, 8, 17], the population of the above-mentioned microorganisms develops consistently, is closely related to the internal environment of the organism and its surrounding environment, reacts to its state. One of the most important functions of the oral microbiome is the maintenance of specific, nonspecific, humoral and cellular immune mechanisms. Bifidobacteria promote the development of lymphocytes, the synthesis of immunoglobulins, the increase of propearin and complement, the activation of lysozyme, the decrease in the permeability of the tissue membrane barrier, the prevention of the onset of bacteremia and sepsis, etc. At the same time, many bacterial species present on the surface of teeth and periodontal pockets produce lipopolysaccharides (endotoxins), carboxylic acids, hydrolases, proteolytic enzymes and other metabolites, causing a cascade of immunological processes that cause inflammation and destruction of periodontal cells. Each strain of Streptococcus mutans, Streptococcus mitis, Streptococcus salivarius, Streptococcus sanguis, Lactobacillus, Actinomyces israelii, Actinomyces viscosus, Actinomyces naeslundii is mainly used to ferment sugars such as sucrose into organic acids such as malic acid, pyruvic acid, lactic acid and formic acid, destroying the tooth enamel, from which it is absorbed. It elutes calcium and fluorine. As a result, the oral cavity resident microorganism is often associated with 2 major infectious and inflammatory diseases, caries and

periodontal disease (a complex of tissues that surround and hold teeth in pyorrhea alveolar). Its development is also dependent on the state and structure of the oral mucosa and gum pockets, the state of the teeth, saliva temperature, pH, properties, secretion rate, chemical composition, nutritional status, oral hygiene status, and peculiarities of oral respiration.[7][7]. According to the World Health Organization (WHO), in most developed countries, caries accounts for 60-90% of young and adults, while in Asian and Latin American countries it accounts for 100%. In Russia, more than 80% of the population suffers from caries [11]. The more carious teeth in the oral cavity, the later their treatment is delayed, the faster the damage to the periodontal tissue. When the hygiene and physical condition of the oral cavity deteriorates, periodontitis begins, a natural pathogenesis with minor symptoms (bloodstains and bad breath when brushing teeth), periodontitis progresses for many years, characterized by the complete destruction of all periodontal tissues, causing loss of teeth, speech disorders and chewing disorders. In addition, the infected nest in the periodontal pocket can adversely affect the entire body and even life-threatening. Periodontal disease affects 98% of the world's adult population. In Russia, intact periodontal membranes are found only in 12% of the population, 53% have early inflammatory phenomena, and 12% have moderate to severe lesions. The prevalence of periodontal disease in adults is 82% [4, 13]. The development of periodontitis is mainly associated with the action of a mixed infection of bacteria and yeast in combination with anaerobic bacteria. Among the periodontogenic microbial complexes, anaerobic bacteria *Aggregatibacter actinomycetemcomitans*, *Porphyromonas gingivalis*, *Tannerella forsythia*, and *Treponema denticola* are distinguished for their highly aggressive tendency to parasitism in the gingival epithelium and periodontal tissues [3, 4]. Overcoming the periodontal epithelium and provoking inflammatory processes, it hematologically moves to other parts of the body. There is much evidence in the scientific literature about the complication of inflammatory periodontal lesions with visceral diseases. First, many researchers

have concluded on the etiological commonality of systemic periodontitis with aortic, coronary and peripheral vascular lesions and atherosclerosis [1, 3].V.I.Haraszthy et al. [21] Studied atherosclerotic plaques in the human carotid artery using polymerase chain reaction (PCR), and found chlamydia pneumoniae, human cytomegalovirus, and bacterial 16S rRNA among them.F.Cairo et al. [20] 79% *Tannerella forsythensis*, 63% *Fusobacterium nucleatum*, 53% *Prevotella intermedia*, and *P. gingivalis* was recognized in 37% and *Actinobacillus actinomycetemcomitans* in 5%.A.Pucar et al. [28] Identified the same bacteria in the aorta and arterioles with arteriosclerotic lesions.A little later, K.Nakano et al. [26] Reports that *Aggativacter actinomycetemcomitans*, *streptococcus mutans*, *streptococcus sanguinis*, *prevotera gingivaris*, and *Treponema dentikola* were detected in aortic plaques and plaques collected from heart valves.There is also evidence that bacteria are acting directly on the endothelial cells of blood vessels.In 2012, the American Heart Association published results that analyzed 537 literature and confirmed that periodontal disease affects the development of atherosclerosis.[3]This happens in 2 ways: bacteria in the bloodstream invade the vascular endothelium, causing endothelial dysfunction, inflammation, atherosclerosis or indirectly stimulating the production of a mediator with atherosclerotic • inflammatory systemic action [24]., 32].The invasion and survival of *Streptococcus mutans*, *Prevotella gingivalis*, and *Prevotella intermedia* bacteria into the aortic endothelial cells was confirmed in in vitro experiments.O.A.A study by Gulyaeva et al.[4] states:[4] states the following facts: When periodontitis becomes severe, the risk of myocardial infarction is 3 times greater, the risk of arteriosclerosis and stroke is 2 times greater, the risk of osteoporosis is 4 times greater, the risk of diabetes is 2-11 times greater, the risk of chronic bronchitis is 2-4 times greater, and the risk of complications during pregnancy is 4-8 times greater.Microbiological studies of atherosclerotic plaques in the human carotid artery detected not only *porphyromonas gingivaris* and *Streptococcus sanguis*, but

also actinobacillus. Using the PCR method, Actinobacillus actinomycetemcomitans, Porphyromonas gingivalis, Bacteroides forsythus, Treponema denticola and Campylobacter rectus were confirmed from the atherosclerotic plaque of the coronary artery. Actinobacillus actinomycetemcomitans, Porphyromonas gingivalis, Prevotella nigrescens, Fusobacterium nucleatum periodonticum and Tannerella forsythia were proven to be present in coronary atheroma. The same PCR method detected Aggregatibacter actinomycetemcomitans in 19.7% of patients with acute myocardial infarction, Porphyromonas gingivalis in 3.4%, and Treponema denticola in 2.3%. A.F. Eliseeva [5] found Treponema forsythensis, Treponema denticola, Porphyromonas gingivalis, and their combination with Chlamydia trachomatis in periodontal pocket and cardiovascular contents in chronic generalized periodontitis associated with coronary heart disease. Porphyromonas gingivalis is thought to induce platelet aggregation by infiltrating endothelial cells and participate in vascular thrombosis. Many streptococci (mainly *S. viridans*, *S. sanguinis*, *S. gordonii*, *S. A. mutans*, *s. mitis*) can also induce platelet adhesion and aggregation in vitro. Many studies have shown that periodontal bacteria stimulate the secretion of inflammatory cytokines and mediators to promote the development of arteriosclerosis. Thus, for the relationship between the periodontogenic microbiome and the development of atherosclerosis and cardiovascular disease, sufficient information even in such a small number of data has been obtained. Because the oral cavity is close to the respiratory tract, it becomes a storehouse of respiratory infections, especially pneumonia. 30-40% of aspiration pneumonia and lung abscesses are caused by the anaerobic bacteria Actinobacillus actinomycetemcomitans, porphyromonas guillain • Haemophilus fungi were detected more frequently in the bronchi of asthmatic and COPD patients. In patients with COPD, changes in the oral mucosa are similar to those in patients with heart failure. Oral bacteria can also cause emphysema and candidiasis. It has been

previously observed that inflammatory periodontal disease is involved in pathologies of the digestive system due to morphological similarity, common innervation and humoral regulation.[7] Many authors say this is because *Helicobacter pylori*, which affects more than 50% of the world's adult population, is proliferating in the oral cavity [16, 18, 29]. The frequency of detection of this microorganism in the stomach increases with age and is correlated with the socioeconomic status of the population [25]. The presence of *Helicobacter pylori* in plaque, saliva and gum pockets ranges from 0 to 100%, noting that all authors rely on poor oral hygiene. However, most researchers who analyzed the causal relationship between periodontal disease and the digestive tract have come to the conclusion that the pathology of the digestive organs always precedes the appearance of periodontal disease.[9] M.V. Safronova et al. [12] Found periodontal disease in 77.6% of patients with chronic gastritis, duodenitis, erosion, peptic ulcer, duodenogastric reflux, and 100% of patients with chronic hepatitis. E.R. Tamarova and A.R. Mavzyutov's study [14] highlights that with periodontitis, cardiovascular disease is diagnosed in 32.1% of cases, with hypertension 17.9%, ischemic heart disease 14.2%, endocrine system diseases (mainly diabetes) 29.2%, and digestive system diseases 28.6%. That is, systemic diseases with periodontitis accounted for 80.2%, and systemic diseases without periodontitis accounted for only 47.0%. The main periodontal agents were *Porphyromonas gingivalis*, *Treponema denticola*, *Streptococcus mutans*, *Streptococcus oralis*, *Streptococcus salivarius*, *Streptococcus sanguis*, *Streptococcus macacae*, and *Streptococcus sobrinus*. There are also reports that AIDS, squamous cell lichen, pancreatic cancer, leukemia, osteoporosis, etc. are associated with oral pathology. Periodontal tissue itself, thyroid, parathyroid, gonadal, liver, kidney, nervous system, endocrine system, otolaryngology system, collagen disease, suffering from hypofunction and hyperactivity, such as allergic diseases. Thus, the prevalence of periodontal disease has increased sharply and has acquired the importance of general medical and social

problems. At present, a lot of evidence on the combination of chronic inflammatory periodontal lesions and visceral diseases has been accumulated. Dentists, along with a full dental examination, must resort to the examination and examination of family doctors and general practitioners, as well as to assess the unfavorable effects of external factors (nutrition, climate) and local factors (sources of chronic microorganisms in the oral cavity).

Conclusion: Therefore, these specialists need to know the quantitative and qualitative composition of the microbiome of an individual human biotope, and in the event that the patient is hospitalized or the condition is deteriorating, it is necessary to exclude the possibility of negative effects of microorganisms in the oral cavity on the course of the body processes.

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